

A COMMON, OPEN SOURCE INTERFACE
BETWEEN EARTH OBSERVATION DATA
INFRASTRUCTURES AND FRONT-END
APPLICATIONS

Deliverable 13

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openEO architecture specification, first version

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List of Acronyms

API Application Programming Interface

EO Earth Observation

HTTP Hypertext Transfer Protocol

openEO Name of the project for which this report was written

REST Representational State Transfer

WCS Web Coverage Service

1 Introduction

The EU funded project openEO develops interfaces (APIs) and libraries for connecting multiple clients (user-side software) to multiple back-ends (server-side software). The goal is that a client that can operate one back-end can also operate all other back-ends supporting the same API. The advantage of this is interoperability, meaning that more systems can work with each other. As a consequence, not only less software needs to be written, but users can compare, using a single client, offerings of different back-ends, in terms of pricing but also in terms of whether identical requests to different servers return identical results.

The openEO will enable researchers to work on a *data cube* of the EO imagery and directly filter, aggregate or map functions over dimensions of a cube (e.g. spatial, temporal, spectral) without being concerned about how the data in the processing platform is organised (by granule, as collections of GRIB or NetCDF files, as one or several arrays in an array database, etc.). To reach this goal, existing back-end systems need to be adapted (or interfaced) to fit the new openEO core API. In its first phase, the openEO project has designed a core API and implemented a number of client libraries that communicate with back-ends. Libraries provide a client API which allows using syntax and conventions native for a programming language.

This document describes openEO architecture that specifies how components developed by the project, such as clients libraries and back-end-drivers, can be utilised to build interoperable systems.

1.1 Purpose

This document provides a comprehensive architectural overview of the openEO ecosystem, using a number of different architectural views to depict different aspects of the system. It is intended to capture and convey the significant architectural decisions which have been made on the system.

Aim of this document is to describe how the APIs and software developed by the openEO project can be used by researchers and back-end operators to become openEO compatible. To do this, we describe a reference architecture that serves as a template for software architectures implemented using components delivered by the openEO project.

1.2 Scope

This document describes reference architecture that specifies how components developed by the project, such as clients libraries or back-end drivers, can be utilised to build interoperable systems compatible with openEO.

openEO does not develop a single system or platform, but develops a set of software components that can be used by various stakeholders to build interoperable systems – each system having its own architecture. For example, libraries and interfaces developed by openEO can be adopted by:

- any back-end operator to make his/her server compatible with the openEO core API,
- any researcher to implement a client connecting to a back-end of his/her choice in any programming language.

For this reason, this document does not focus on specific software architecture of components developed within the project. Such components are described in respective deliverables - see Section 2 for references to other deliverables.

It also does not describe physical architecture, that is, details how specific components, for example back-end drivers, are deployed in concrete locations. This is because the outputs of the project can be used by anyone everywhere.

1.3 Overview

This document is organised as follows:

- Section 1 presents the introduction and outlines the scope of the document.
- Section 2 provides references to other openEO deliverables.
- Section 3 explains notation used in diagrams.
- Section 4 describes the current situation and presents the motivation for the openEO architecture.
- Section 5 describes architectural goals and constraints that affect the openEO architecture.
- Section 6 presents openEO architecture with a use of different views.
- Section 7 describes alternative architectures considered.

2 References to other deliverables

Connections to other openEO deliverables published to date:

- **D04 openEO core API prototype including Proof of Concept**
 - The openEO core API is one of the main motivations for this project and has influence on the architecture, because it implies that the communication between clients and back-ends will follow a client–server template.
 - D04 deliverable focuses on the functionality offered by the openEO core API, this in turn influences functionalities that will be provided by compatible back-ends and clients.
 - This document describing architecture does not deal with the functionality of the openEO core API, because this one was described in the D04 deliverable and will be described in the subsequent deliverables focusing on the API.
- **D05 Overview document about back offices metadata standards and interfaces**
 - Deliverable D05 describes standards and interfaces running in the back-ends, which have impact on the requirements that drive the architecture described in this document.

- This document describing openEO architecture does not deal with the way back-ends implement specific drivers. Deployment is highly back-end specific. Some details can be provided in the revised version of this document in month 25 of the project.
- **D06 Two early prototype back-ends**
 - Back-end drivers described in deliverable D06 are elements needed to deploy architecture described in this document.
- **D07 Proof of Concept (Python)**
 - A prototype of a client software used to connect to back-ends that use core API is described in D07. Deliverable D07 instantiates architecture described in this deliverable.
- **D09 First overview of needed processes from use cases**
 - Deliverable D09 describes requirements that have impact on the requirements for the architecture described in this document.

3 Notation used

This document is structured using Rational Unified Process architecture document template¹. It reflects the Kruchten's 4+1 method [3] and follows viewpoint-oriented architecture.

Viewpoints define abstractions on the set of models representing architecture, each aimed at a particular type of stakeholder and addressing a particular set of concerns [1]. For example a viewpoint can show logical view, processing view, deployment view, and implementation view. It is up to the architect to decide which views are relevant and necessary to present a given architecture.

We use ArchiMate 3.0.1 notation² to produce different architectural views. The ArchiMate modelling language is an open and independent Enterprise Architecture standard that supports the description, analysis and visualisation of architecture within and across business domains. ArchiMate is one of the open standards hosted by The Open Group³ and is fully aligned with TOGAF [4].

In most diagrams we used the layered view that depicts architecture on three different levels (so called layers):

- *business layer* (yellow colour) – to depict stakeholders, goals, and processes executed,
- *application layer* (blue colour) – to describe the structure and interaction of the applications,
- *technology layer* (green colour) – to describe platform services, and logical and physical technology components.

¹http://sce.uhcl.edu/helm/RationalUnifiedProcess/webtmpl/templates/a_and_d/rup_sad.htm

²<http://pubs.opengroup.org/architecture/archimate3-doc/toc.html>

³<http://www.opengroup.org>

Figure 3.1: ISO25010 - software product quality [2]

Each of the layers allows us to focus on specific aspects of the architecture. Table 3.1 provides an overview of elements used in the models and their meaning.

For sequence diagrams we used traditional UML syntax.

We used ISO 25010⁴ product quality model for non-functional requirements (see Figure 3.1) to set goals for the openEO architecture in Section 5.

Table 3.1: Overview of ArchiMate concepts used in the diagrams to depict the openEO architecture [1].

		Business actor	A business entity that is capable of performing behavior.
		Business role	The responsibility for performing specific behavior, to which an actor can be assigned, or the part an actor plays in a particular action or event.
		Business process	A sequence of business behaviors that achieves a specific outcome such as a defined set of products or business services.
		Business event	A business behavior element that denotes an organizational state change. It may originate from and be resolved inside or outside the organization.

⁴<http://iso25000.com/index.php/en/iso-25000-standards/iso-25010>

	<p>Application component</p>	<p>An encapsulation of application functionality aligned to implementation structure, which is modular and replaceable. It encapsulates its behavior and data, exposes services, and makes them available through interfaces.</p>
	<p>Application interface</p>	<p>A point of access where application services are made available to a user, another application component, or a node.</p>
	<p>Application function</p>	<p>Automated behavior that can be performed by an application component.</p>
	<p>Data Object</p>	<p>Data structured for automated processing.</p>
	<p>Node</p>	<p>A computational or physical resource that hosts, manipulates, or interacts with other computational or physical resources.</p>
	<p>System software</p>	<p>Software that provides or contributes to an environment for storing, executing, and using software or data deployed within it.</p>
	<p>Path</p>	<p>A link between two or more nodes, through which these nodes can exchange data or material.</p>
	<p>Artifact</p>	<p>An artifact represents a piece of data that is used or produced in a software development process, or by deployment and operation of an IT system.</p>

Figure 4.1: Layered view depicting current situation (before the openEO project) - researchers need to reimplement their code when switching between back-ends.

4 Architectural representation ('as is')

End users in order to run their code on different back-ends must implement code that is compatible with an interface of a specific back-end. Hence, the code is not easily portable. Figure 4.1 depicts this situation: each back-end can run different software for processing data; each of back-ends can offer different access interface. For this reason researchers must re-implement their experiments for each back-end.

5 Architectural Goals and Constraints

This section describes the software requirements and objectives that have significant impact on the proposed openEO architecture. It also describes technical and business context which impact the design of the proposed openEO architecture.

5.1 Goals and Requirements

We used the ISO 25010 quality requirements (cf. Section 3) to identify goals relevant for the proposed openEO architecture. For each of the identified goals we defined requirements that have impact on the proposed architecture.

- **G1. Compatibility**

- **G1.1 Interoperability**

- * R1.1 openEO architecture must not be limited to a specific programming language, technology or back-end architecture.
 - * R1.2 Source code implemented using openEO libraries that conform to the openEO core API must be runnable on compatible back-ends.

- **G1.2 Co-existence**

- * R1.3 openEO architecture must provide an alternative way to access computational resources and data without affecting existing means.

- **G2. Portability**

- **G2.1 Installability**

- * R2.1 Components of the openEO architecture must be provided in a standard way for a given environment, e.g. python client libraries as python modules.

- **G2.2 Adaptability**

- * R2.2 It must be possible to adapt the openEO architecture to evolving hardware and software.

- **G3. Performance efficiency**

- R3.1 openEO architecture must not affect performance of existing systems, e.g. by creating computational bottlenecks.

5.2 Context and Constraints

The organisational and technical context is depicted in Figure 5.1. It consists of following elements:

- End users – users who write code, using programming language of their choice, or define their experiments using a visual editor. In both cases their experiments are executed on back-ends.
- Back-end operators – stakeholders who provide infrastructure and access to data used in earth observation experiments.
- End user system – system used by researchers to implement their code. It connects over the Internet to back-ends to execute code.

Figure 5.1: Organisational and technical context that sets requirements for the openEO architecture.

- Back-end server – system in which code written by researchers is executed. This system accesses EO data and produces results using software that was installed by back-end operator.

The proposed openEO architecture can modify existing systems, but must fit into the existing context, hence fulfilling following requirements:

- R4 openEO architecture must follow client-server architecture.
- R5 Raw⁵ data must be kept at the back-end server.
- R6 Computations must be performed at the back-end server.
- R7 Existing back-end software used for computations must be reused.
- R8 Users must connect to back-ends over the Internet from their own systems.

6 openEO Architecture ('to be')

This section describes the proposed openEO architecture which fulfils the objectives described in Section 5. Alternative approaches considered are described in Section 7. In the following subsections we use a set of views to depict the architecture taking into account different architectural viewpoints (cf. Section 3).

6.1 Use case view

Figure 6.1 depicts a simplified typical process executed by researchers working using openEO architecture.

Researcher who is an openEO user does his/her analysis by writing code on a local machine. The code is later executed as a job on the back-end server. openEO user downloads the results from the back-end server to the local machine and continues the analysis locally.

In the remainder of this document we use this process to depict different views on the openEO architecture. For simplicity, we depict only parts of this process, for example, only *Run job* process step.

⁵Raw in the sense that it is the original data provided by the back-end, which could be pre-processed.

Figure 6.1: Simplified typical process executed by an openEO user.

6.2 Building block view - level 1

Figure 6.2 depicts the high level building block view of the openEO architecture that follows the client–server architecture.

- Business layer (yellow)
 - *openEO user* run jobs using *openEO client API*.
- Application layer (blue)
 - *Implementation of Experiment* is a program/script written by the user that contains experiments logic (not depicted) and includes *openEO client* that handles communication with back-ends.
 - *openEO client* consists of the *openEO client API* that provides methods to work with the *openEO core API* using programming language chosen by the *openEO user*.
 - *openEO client* connects to the *openEO back-end driver* that has an interface compliant with the *openEO core API*.
 - *openEO back-end driver* is an application running on a back-end server that handles requests received from the *client* application.
- Infrastructure layer (green)
 - Communication between the *end user system* and the *back-end server* is realised over *Internet*.

6.3 Building block view - level 2

Figure 6.3 depicts the same building block view as in Figure 6.2 but provides more details.

- Business layer
 - *openEO users* run jobs.
 - *Back-end operator* becomes an *openEO compatible back-end operator* by implementing an *openEO core API* that helps in realising *interoperability*.
 - *Interoperability* is a shared goal for *researchers* and *back-end operators*.

Figure 6.2: openEO architecture - building block view - level 1: key components of the openEO architecture.

- Application layer

- *openEO client* communicates with the *openEO back-end driver* using the *openEO core API*.
- *openEO client* offers functionalities that reflect functionality defined by the *openEO core API*. In the provide example, client offers functionality for job managing.
- *openEO client API* offers the same functionality as the *openEO core API* - in the depicted example *Job Management*. The difference is that the *openEO client API* provides convenient methods specific for a programming language to communicate with a back-end, while the *openEO core API* is independent of a programming language and uses HTTP as a communication protocol⁶. Thus, *openEO users* who use *openEO client API* do not have to construct and parse HTTP requests and responses, but can use convenient methods native for the programming language of their choice.
- *openEO client* requires *connection details* to connect to a selected back-end. These connection details are provided by the *openEO user*.
- *openEO back-end driver* application implements interface compliant with the *openEO core API*.
- *openEO back-end driver* application implements functionalities that reflect functionality defined by the *openEO core API*. In the provide example, back-end driver offers functionality for job managing.

⁶Other related protocols such as WebSockets may be used for specialised sub-tasks of the API.

Figure 6.3: openEO architecture - building block view - level 2: key components of the openEO architecture in detail.

- Infrastructure layer

- *openEO client* is a piece of software that uses *openEO library* that offers functions compatible with the *openEO core API* specification. Thus, the library handles the HTTP calls on behalf of the user.
- *openEO back-end driver* is an application that implements the *openEO core API* interface.
- *openEO back-end driver* is in most instances a facade for the underlying *geo software* that is installed in the *back-end server*.
- *Geo software* represents any type of software used for manipulating earth observation data that is of relevance to the openEO.

6.4 Runtime view

This section depicts the runtime view. It presents two scenarios that are variances of the use case presented in Section 6.1.

The openEO architecture does not impact client and back-end driver design and their implementation when it comes to synchronous/asynchronous calls or parallelism of jobs execution. This is defined by the openEO core API specification.

Figure 6.4: Runtime view: UML sequence diagram depicting creation of jobs at the back-end by the client.

6.4.1 Scenario 1 - standard conversation

Figure 6.4 is an UML sequence diagram depicting the first scenario. Client communicates with the back-end driver following a typical client-server scheme for HTTP conversations:

1. *Client* sends a request to create a job to the *back-end driver*. *Back-end driver* stores the request.
2. *Client* sends a request to start the job. *Back-end driver* passes the job to the *Geo software* that runs the job. Job is run asynchronously (client can poll the back-end driver to find out whether the job has finished – this is not depicted in the diagram).
3. *Client* sends a request to access job results.
4. *Back-end driver* sends a document to the *client* pointing to one or more URLs where the results of the job are accessible.

6.4.2 Scenario 2 - using external web services

Second scenario describes a case in which the openEO core API is used to process data and control external web services. Such web services are later accessed using different interfaces than the openEO core API – this is one of the requirements (see R1.4 in Section 5). Figure 6.5 depicts an UML sequence diagram for publishing job results through a WCS service:

1. *Client* sends a request to create a job to the *back-end driver*.
2. *Back-end driver* passes the request to the *Geo software* running in the server.
3. *Geo software* starts the job and sends back confirmation to the *back-end driver*.

Figure 6.5: Runtime view: UML sequence diagram depicting creation of jobs at the back-end and publishing their results using a WCS web service.

Figure 6.6: Deployment view - overview

4. *Back-end driver* sends confirmation to the *client* that the job was created.
5. *Client* sends a request to the *back-end driver* to start a WCS service.
6. *Back-end driver* starts the *WCS service* and sends back the service URL.
7. *Web browser* sends a request to access the job results to the WCS server (note: WCS service is accessed using different means than the openEO client!).
8. *WCS service* sends request to the *Geo software* to process the job. *Geo software* executes the job that was scheduled by the *back-end driver*.
9. *WCS service* sends results back to the web browser.
10. *Client* sends a request to the *back-end driver* to stop the web service.
11. *Back-end driver* stops the service and responds with a confirmation.

6.5 Deployment view

Architecture described in this document is reference architecture. This means that it should be used as a template and the actual deployment can be performed in various ways. In this section we describe three views that cover most typical deployments that we foresee.

6.5.1 Deployment - overview

Figure 6.6 presents the deployment view of the architecture:

- There are at least two nodes needed to deploy the openEO components:
 - at least one *back-end server* that runs *back-end driver* conform to the *core API* specification,
 - at least one *end user system* with a *client library* conforming to the core API specification.
- *Back-end server* is operated by the *back-end operator* who deploys a *back-end driver*.
 - *Back-end driver* can be found on the *openEO GitHub* and is provided by *openEO developers*.
 - *Back-end driver* integrates with the *Geo software* installed in the server and acts as a facade.
 - *Back-end driver* communicates with the external clients using *HTTP*.
- *End user system* is operated by an *openEO user*.
 - *openEO user* downloads openEO libraries/modules from software repositories, such as *Maven*, *PyPi*, etc., and deploys it into their environment.
 - *openEO user* writes scripts in the programming language of his/her choice (for which he/she downloaded the library/module) to communicate with the *back-end server*.

Figure 6.7: Deployment view: client can communicate with multiple back-ends without re-implementing code, thanks to openEO core API.

6.5.2 Deployment – various back-ends

One of the main goals for the openEO architecture was to enable clients to access various back-ends running different geo software in a unified way. To achieve this each back-end provider must deploy a back-end driver that integrates with the underlying processing software, and expose a HTTP interface compatible with the openEO core API specification. This is depicted in Figure 6.7.

6.5.3 Deployment – various clients

openEO core API is independent of any programming language. For this reason, client libraries can be implemented in any programming language. Such libraries are used by the openEO users to interact with back-ends. Thus, the users can call back-ends using syntax and following conventions that are native for the programming language of their choice. The client libraries, e.g. *Python Client* or *R Client* (see Figure 6.8) interact with back-ends using the openEO core API.

Figure 6.8: Deployment view: clients implemented in any programming language can communicate with the back-end thanks to the openEO core API.

7 Alternatives considered

This section describes two alternative architectures. Alternative A that uses proxy service and which was rejected, it does not meet project goals, such as, performance efficiency. Alternative B that uses a registry of available back-ends and which can be created by extending the proposed architecture in the later stages of the project.

7.1 Alternative A - Proxy service

Architecture that uses a proxy service requires a third party running dedicated services that forwards all communication between clients and back-end drivers. Communication flows through a central proxy node.

7.1.1 Building block view

Figure 7.1 depicts the integrated view of the architecture that uses proxy node:

- *openEO users* can select a *back-end* to which they want to connect using functionality provided by the *openEO client*. This functionality is supported by the *openEO core API*.
- *Clients* communicate with the *openEO proxy*, but not with the *openEO back-end driver*.
- *openEO proxy* communicates using additional API with the *back-end driver*. In the diagram the additional API is called the *driver API*.
- *openEO driver API* mirrors most of the functionality of the *core API*, but extends it with functionality that is needed for communication between the proxy node and back-ends.
- *Back-end operators* register nodes at the proxy. Otherwise the back-ends cannot be used.

Figure 7.1: Building block view - considered alternative for the openEO architecture that uses proxy service.

7.1.2 Runtime view

Figure 7.2 depicts an UML sequence diagram depicting process view for the considered architecture:

1. *Client* asks the proxy node for the list of available back-ends.
2. *Proxy* sends back the list of back-ends that are registered.
3. *Client* creates a new job in a select back-end by sending a request to the proxy node.
4. *Proxy* node communicates with a selected back-end and forwards the request to the back-end driver.
5. *Back-end driver* executes the job by calling geo software installed at the back-end.
6. *Client* downloads job results by sending a request to the proxy.
7. *Proxy* forwards the request to the back-end driver.
8. *Back-end driver* collects the results from the geo software and sends back an URL.
9. *Proxy* service provides the URL to the client.

7.1.3 Summary

- Advantages
 - users do not have to know connection details for specific back-ends
 - easier discovery of new back-ends through API functions

Figure 7.2: Runtime view - considered alternative for the openEO architecture that uses proxy service.

- Disadvantages
 - all traffic is routed through a single service
 - * this creates a single point of failure
 - * can affect performance and cause bottlenecks
 - * can raise privacy issues
 - requires an additional stakeholder to operate the proxy node
 - longer processing chain

7.2 Alternative B - Registry service

This considered alternative uses a registry of back-ends which can be looked up using the openEO API to get a list of available back-ends. Similar to the proxy solution described above it requires an additional node to run the registry. The difference is that the communication between the client and the back-end is direct and the registry is only used to look-up connection details using core API functions.

7.2.1 Building block view

Figure 7.3 depicts the integrated view of the architecture that uses registry.

- *openEO users* selects a *back-end* to which they want to connect using functionality provided by the openEO client. This functionality is supported by the openEO core API.

Figure 7.3: Building block view - considered alternative for the openEO architecture that uses registry to look up information on available back-ends.

- *Back-end operator* registers their back-end in the back-end registry.
- *Back-end registry* is run by a registry operator on an independent node.
- *Back-end registry* contains a list of registered back-ends.
- *Client* communicates over HTTP (using the openEO core API) directly with the selected back-end for running jobs.

7.2.2 Runtime view

1. *Client* asks the *back-end registry* for a list of available back-ends.
2. *Back-end registry* sends back a list of back-ends that got registered by their back-end operators.
3. *Client* selects a back-end and then communicates with it directly
4. *Client* sends a request to create a job to the back-end driver.
5. *Back-end driver* passes the request to the *Geo software* running in the server.
6. *Geo software* starts the job and sends back confirmation to the *back-end driver*.
7. *Back-end driver* sends confirmation to the *client* that the job was created. Job is run asynchronously (client can poll the back-end driver to find out whether the job has finished - this is not depicted in the diagram).
8. *Client* sends a request to access job results.
9. *Back-end driver* sends an URL to the client those points to the results of the job.

Figure 7.4: Runtime view - considered alternative for the openEO architecture that uses registry to look up information on available back-ends.

7.2.3 Summary

- Advantages
 - users do not have to know connection details for specific back-ends
 - easier discovery of new back-ends through API functions
 - clients interact directly with selected back-ends
- Disadvantages
 - requires additional stakeholder to operate and maintain the registry

8 References

- [1] The Open Group, *ArchiMate 3.0 Specification*. Van Haren Publishing, 2016.
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